

ISic1182

I.Sicily inscription 1182

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Apollonia

Place of origin (modern)

Monte San Fratello

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Monte San Fratello

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140665

1. [— —]ΕΛΕΥΣΥΝΑ [—]

2. ΤΕ[— —]ΟΜΟΧΩΡΙΟΥ

3. ΑΟ [— — — — —]

4. Εὐλώιον {²⁷Ἐπ [ι] λώιον (?) }²⁷ Εὐξένου.

5. θεοῖς.

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492787

EDCS 39102336

PHI 140665

Bibliography

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Castelli, Gabriele Lancillotto, principe di Torremuzza 1769. Siciliae et objacentium insularum veterum inscriptionum nova collectio. Panormus. At cl.18 no.31

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5604

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 197 no.15

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